

Negotiating between Communication and Cooperation for Multiple Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

Daniel Pack, Glen Dudevoir, Pedro Lima, and Scott Gruber
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
US Air Force Academy
USAF Academy, CO 80840
{*daniel.pack, glen.dudevoir, pedro.lima, scott.gruber@usafa.edu*}

Abstract

The emerging technologies of multiple, cooperative unmanned systems have brought in an exciting period of possibilities, possibilities of solving challenging problems in medical, social, engineering, and military communities. The technologies have also introduced a growing number of new challenges such as resource allocation, communication and coordination, establishment of consensus, and control optimization among cooperative systems. In this paper, we address one of these challenges for cooperative unmanned aerial systems (UASs): trade-off between maintaining communication reliability among, and collective target search efforts by, a team of unmanned systems. We evaluate the impact on the overall search capability of a cooperative system when the movements of its members are constrained due to the requirement of communication reliability. Our comparative study is based on an adaptation of work reported in [3] and we show our findings using simulation and flight experiment results.

Keywords: cooperative control, communication network

1. Introduction

Over the past five years, researchers at the US Air Force Academy have been developing a team of autonomous, cooperative unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) capable of performing a variety of military missions. The flight missions demonstrated include persistent intelligence collection, surveillance, and reconnaissance (ISR) of designated areas using multiple UAVs, autonomous rendezvous of UAVs over operator designated locations, and detection and localization of ground targets using both ground and air networks of sensors. One of our current research interests is finding

solutions to maintain communication reliability among cooperative UAVs while maximizing collective sensor coverage of the UAVs during a search mission. In this paper, we address this problem by making a comparative study of two distributive search algorithms. In the next section, we briefly describe the collective control capabilities of our cooperative UAVs. In Section III, we describe the two distributive search methods, followed by simulation and flight experimental results in section IV. We complete the paper with a few concluding remarks.

2. Cooperative UAV system

We desire our system of multiple cooperative UAVs to be autonomous, distributive, and scalable. To that end, we have developed distributive control technologies, local sensor fusion capabilities[2, 4], and a unique operating system for unmanned systems. For the communication network, we adopted the IEEE 802.11g multi-hop mesh network system. In this section the mission is for a team of UAVs to cooperatively search, detect, and locate ground targets to illustrate the existing cooperative control architecture. Figure 1 shows a picture of a typical UAV we use in our experiments. The control module placed on each UAV uses a behavior-based, distributed, cooperative algorithm. Control decision for the UAVs are computed in real-time, using an onboard computer, based on current sensor data, mission objectives, and the data it receives from neighboring UAVs (telemetry and sensor data). Each UAV, using a behavior-based state machine, independently computes flight trajectories to minimize the combined search cost, which is a function of search coverage, time, and fuel usage. There are four states in which a UAV can operate for the mission: (1) global search for targets (GS), (2) approach detected target (AT), (3) locate target (LT), and (4) local search for lost targets (LS). When the movements of a set of UAVs

Figure 1: A photo of the unmanned aerial vehicle

are combined together, they collectively complete the overall desired task of searching, detecting and localizing all ground targets. Figure 2 shows the state diagram of the control architecture for a single UAV.

Figure 2: The state diagram governs the behavior of each UAV. This figure shows the transition paths between the GS, AT, LT, and LS states for a single UAV.

At the start of the mission, all UAVs operate in the Global Search (GS) state. The movements of a UAV in this state are governed by a set of rules [3] to minimize a search cost function such as flying away from other UAVs and maintaining the current direction of flight if possible. By evaluating the search cost continually while operating at this state, a UAV constantly updates its direction of flight to increase the probability of detecting ground targets. It is during this stage of the mission that the communication reliability among UAVs determines the effectiveness of the cooperative search coverage of the mission area, which prompted the current study.

Once a target is detected by a UAV, each UAV that receives the target detection information through the communication network uses the following equation to

determine whether or not to participate in localizing the detected target (switch to Approach Target (AT) state) or to continue searching for other targets that have not yet been detected.

$$cost = w_1 \frac{D}{D_{normalized}} - w_2(n - s) + w_3(m - p) \quad (1)$$

Symbols D , $D_{normalized}$, and n represent the estimated Euclidean distance from the current UAV location to the newly detected target, a normalized distance reflecting the size of the entire search area, and the required number of UAVs to accurately locate a target, respectively. Symbols s , m , and p denote the number of UAVs currently engaged in state Locate Target (LT) or state Local Search (LS) for the specified target, the total estimated number of targets in the search space, and the number of targets that have been detected or located, respectively. Finally, symbols w_i 's are the weights that can be used to influence the behavior of a UAV. With the exceptions of w_i 's and $D_{normalized}$, all other variables are updated continuously as a UAV traverses in the search space.

When a UAV reaches an estimated target localization orbit, an orbit around the estimated target location, (shown as the smaller circles in Figure 4) the operating state automatically changes from AT to LT. Once a UAV enters the LT state, it coordinates its flying speed with other UAVs on the same orbit to fly in an equi-angle apart formation. This task is performed by communication among UAVs that are cooperatively locating a target.

Finally, a UAV may enter the fourth state if the target is lost (signal transmission stops or target moves out of the sensor range) while a localization process is taking place but has not been completed. When such situations occur, UAVs that are currently involved in localizing a target switch from the LT state to the LS state where the UAVs gradually increase the radius of the localization orbit over time. The rate of increase is a function of the elapsed time from the last observation of the target and the two past observed target locations. Figure 3 shows a sequence of snapshots showing the entire process of UAVs searching, detecting, and localizing mobile targets.

3. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The current problem of interest is quantifying the trade-off between maximizing the cooperative coverage of a search area by multiple UAVs and maximizing the average bandwidth among the participating UAVs during the search mission. Due to the limitation on the amount of hardware we can carry on our small

Figure 3: Snapshots showing the process of searching for, detecting, and localizing three mobile targets using six UAVs. Frame (a) shows the initial locations of UAVs (larger circles) and targets (smaller circles). Frame (b) shows the search pattern generated when all UAVs are operating in the GS state. Frame (c) shows a target being detected by a UAV, which starts orbiting the target and transmits its discovery of the target to nearby UAVs. Frame (d) shows that two other nearby UAVs have responded to the call and joined the target localization orbit to locate the target. Finally, frame (e) shows that the target have been fully localized, represented by a square.

Figure 4: A snap shot of the graphical simulator: nine UAVs are searching for three targets in the space of 75 km by 75 km.

UAVs, we chose IEEE 802.11g compliant radios with bandwidth limited to 20 MHz as the primary means for UAVs to communicate. To achieve various data rates, different modulation techniques are employed, each requiring known minimum values for received *RF* power. The received RF power can be easily modeled based on the distance between UAVs by using a modified Friis equation 2, which determines a relationship between achievable data rate and distance between UAVs.

$$P_R = \frac{P_T G_T G_R}{d^n L_P L_C} \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where P_R and P_T denote the radio RF power received and transmitted, respectively. For our experiments, all antennas are assumed to be omni-directional with a gain of 1 dBm. The transmitting antenna has a gain of G_T and the receiving antenna has a gain of G_R . The two radios are located d meters apart, and the path loss exponent n characterizes the transmission environment. The values L_P and L_C represent polarization losses occurring as the result of different banking angles of UAVs and cabling (interconnection) losses, respectively. The constant λ is the wavelength of the carrier frequency. For our experiments, all constants were adjusted to be representative of the communication characteristics of small UAVs equipped with the XtremeRange2[©] radio. Specifically, the losses L_P and L_C were both assumed to be 3 dBm each, the wavelength λ was calculated based on a frequency of 2.45 GHz, and the exponent n , which has a value of 2 in an “ideal” environment, was set to 2.2 in order to capture the expected environment losses within the flight area. Table 1 gives the minimum received RF power values of the XtremeRange2 radio for different

Data Rate (Mbps)	Transmit Power (dBm)	Minimum Received Power (dBm)
6	28	-94
9	28	-93
12	28	-91
18	28	-90
24	28	-86
36	26	-83
48	25	-77
54	24	-74

Table 1: XtremeRange2 radio RF power requirements

data rates.

We now describe the methods we used to compare the search performance of our system when it incorporates the communication constraints with the performance of the same system without the communication constraints. The new search algorithm seeks to account for the intention of maintaining high communication bandwidth with neighboring UAVs while performing cooperative search over a large area. As the baseline for comparison, we make use of the original search algorithm introduced in [1]. In the original search algorithm, which does not consider communication constraints, a UAV evaluates four intentionality vectors before determining its next heading direction h . These intentionality vectors are: the goal vector, v_g , that points toward the direction of the greatest gain in search coverage; the UAV separation vector v_{uav} which is a sum of vectors away from neighboring UAVs whose magnitudes are inversely proportional to the distance between each pair; the boundary vector v_c which is a sum of vectors oriented away from the borders of a search area with magnitudes inversely proportional to the distances to boundaries from the UAV; and the momentum vector v_m which is a unit vector oriented along the current heading direction of the UAV for the purpose of reducing the intensity of the aircraft turns in order to conserve fuel.

For the new search algorithm, we added a fifth intentionality vector dedicated to communication quality. The resulting equation used to determine the next UAV heading direction h_c is shown in 3. The intentionality vector for maximization of communication data bandwidth is v_{com} , determined by 4. The degree with which v_{com} impacts a UAV's heading h_c is controlled by the weight w_{com} , just as the contribution of the other vectors are adjusted by their respective weights as prescribed in [1].

$$h_c = w_g v_g + w_{uav} v_{uav} + w_c v_c + w_m v_m + w_{com} v_{com} \quad (3)$$

$$v_{com} = \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq s}}^N \frac{P_R^{max} - P_R(d_{is})}{P_R^{max}(N-1)} \vec{a}_{si} \quad (4)$$

where \vec{a}_{si} is the normalized vector describing the spatial relationship of the UAV with neighboring UAV i . The variable r_{si} encodes the theoretical maximum data rate available for communication between two UAVs, which is a function of the distance between the two UAVs, d_{si} . The maximum value achieved by P_R under a given communication protocol, radios, and environment is P_R^{max} , i.e., $P_R^{max} = P_R(0)$. The total number of UAVs in the team is represented by N .

Note that in this formulation, v_{com} has a magnitude zero when the communication quality among all UAVs is at its maximum, allowing the search to be conducted freely with the original four intentionality vectors. However, the magnitude $|v_{com}|$ increases proportional to the distance between UAVs based on the pre-defined discrete levels of possible maximum data rates. This trend continues until v_{com} reaches the point in which communication is impossible with any other UAV.

4 Experimental Results

We conducted both a high fidelity hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) simulations and flight tests to compare the two methods. The HIL simulator makes use of the same navigation and processing units onboard the UAVs used in the flight experiments. The camera sensor characteristics were also emulated. Moreover, the HIL simulations allow for testing of the algorithm in large search area, which pose a particular challenge to the communication capabilities of the small UAVs.

We performed simulations with two UAVs with the same characteristics and payload as the ones used in the flight experiments to search an area of 40 square kilometers (8km by 5km). Two missions were performed, one with the original search algorithm and the other with the revised search algorithm incorporating

communication constraints. We recorded the search and communication performance of the system for both missions during the initial 30 minutes. The simulations were not subject to the constraint of the limited area available for the flight experiments. For these experiments w_{com} was assigned a value of 1, once more being normalized with the remaining four weights afterwards. As one can see in Fig. 5, the overall communication data rate among UAVs was much higher for significant amounts of time for the method computing h_c compared to the one computing h . On the other hand, Fig. 6 shows that the joint coverage capability of the two UAVs has decreased by a significant amount when the communication constraints were imposed.

Figure 5: Comparison of the portion of the mission time spent in each of the maximum data rate bracket. Average of two simulation (HIL) results.

In addition to the simulation experiment, two flight tests were conducted. In the first one, a team of two UAVs was sent to search an area of one square kilometer using a controller generating headings according to h as described in the previous section. In the second flight, the same UAVs repeated the mission using the new search method to generate h_c . The semi-optimal weights were found using an evolution technique.

Figure 7 shows a comparison of the sensor coverage of the two UAVs during the first 6 minutes (approximately) of the search mission. The short duration of the experiment reflects the small search area where the experiment is performed, due to logistic problems of conducting the experiment in a large area. Note that there is very little difference between the outcomes of

Figure 6: Comparison of the coverage achieved in the first 30 minutes of the mission. Average of two simulation (HIL) results.

the application of the h and h_c , with the search algorithm without communication constraints producing only a slightly better performance. Meanwhile, Fig. 8 illustrates the relative communication performance of the two algorithms by showing the portion of the mission time spent in each data rate level. Under the control algorithm based on h_c , the UAVs spend a greater portion of the time with the 54 Mbps communication bandwidth available (40.7% of the time, compared to 32.2% of the time under the standard algorithm). However, the strategy guided by h_c also resulted in a greater portion of the time at the lowest observed data bandwidth of 24 Mbps (14.0% of the time, compared to 9.8% of the time under the standard algorithm). We attribute the increase in the time spent at the 24 Mbps to the small size of the search area that often caused the UAVs to engage in additional aircraft maneuvers in order to remain within the search area perimeter.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we studied the effect of considering a set of communication constraints in the search coverage performance of multiple cooperative UAVs. The comparative study is shown in the context of multiple UAVs cooperatively searching, detecting, and locating ground targets. We showed that both the simulation and flight experiments support our intuition of the de-

Figure 7: Joint sensor coverage comparison obtained from two flight tests.

Figure 8: Comparison of the portion of the mission time spent in each of the maximum data rate bracket obtained from two flight tests.

graded search capability when the communication constraints among UAVs must be met and quantified the impact to the overall search capability of two cooperative UAVs. The future areas of research are to (1) develop a more detailed 3D antenna patterns, (2) adjust the cooperative search technique to optimize the trade-off between communication constraints and the search coverage capability, and (3) evaluate methods of computing weights used to generate heading directions by considering different evaluation criteria for missions other than the search mission described in this paper.

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